

THE EFFECT OF COMPUTER GRAPHIC ANIMATION COURSEWARE ON NCE STUDENTS' COGNITIVE ACHIEVEMENT IN MACHINE WOODWORKING IN NORTHWEST, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The main objective of the study was to determine the effect of Computer Graphic Animation Courseware (CGAC) on students' cognitive Achievement in machine woodworking in colleges of Education in North West Nigeria. The study was guided by one Research Questions and two Null Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study consisted of 137 NCE students offering Machine woodworking, and the Random Sampling procedure was used to select four out of the twelve Colleges of Education in Northwest, Nigeria. The instruments used for data collection were development by the researcher and both the Machine Woodworking Achievement Test (MWWAT) items and the CGAC were validated by experts and were tested for reliability in which the computed values of .983 and .993 were obtained respectively. The Data collected were analyzed using Mean, Standard deviation and the independent sample t – test statistics was used to compare Means of the two groups; all the two null hypotheses were rejected. The findings of the study provided empirical evidence that supports the basis for inferences to be made to the effect that the use of CGAC was responsible for the improved Achievement of NCE students in Machine woodworking. It was recommended that the National Commission for Colleges of Education and Machine Woodworking Lecturers should urgently adopt the use of the CGAC in the Machine Woodworking teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Effect, Computer Graphic Animation, Machine Woodworking, Cognitive Achievement

Introduction

One of the most used instructional technology tools in today's teaching and learning processes is the Computer Graphic (Multimedia) Animation. It involves the use of transitions and transformation of graphic images which describes the procedure of a concept which may be abstract. The word 'Animation' is derived from the Latin word 'Anima', which means soul; Alyssa (2023) pronounced that the simulation of movement created by a series of pictures is Animation. It is gaining popularity in the world of entertainment and multimedia, apart from being a source of entertainment, animation is also an educational tool. It is a form of art that is celebrated in the world-wide film festival. Basically, there are five types of animation, they include: traditional animation (Hand drawn), 2D animation, 3D animation, Motion graphics and Stop motion.

Achievement can be defined as a thing done successfully, typically by efforts, courage or skill. It is the process of actualizing something and can be grouped into standardized achievement test or teacher made achievement test. According to Zhao (2017), Academic Achievement refers to the actual performance of students' mastery of academic knowledge and

skills as demonstrated through examinations after systematic and skills learning. Both Cognitive and Academic Achievement refers to mental, scholarly or intellectual success; it is described by Adeyemi & Semiu (2014) as the scholastic standing of a student at a given moment which states individual abilities. In other words, they refer to the persons' learning ability which could be positive or negative performance. The outcome of students' cognitive academic achievements could be used for placement of student to a class or for formative or summative purposes as in the case of Junior Secondary School Certificate or the West African School Certificate Examinations and the award of Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), Ordinary Diplomas and Bachelor Degrees. In addition, the academic achievement scores could be used for diagnostic assessment. If the learning ability is positive, it means pass; while it is failure when the learning ability and outcome is negative; high or low performance may depend on a number of factors, top among these factors are the methodology of the teacher. Besides, in Aremu's study (as cited in a survey by Ampadu, Bernice, Amoako, Azamela & Antwi 2019), submitted that many researchers and educators also alluded that negative attitudes towards a subject directly affects the way students react or listen to the teacher; additionally, when students feel or believe that they cannot pass, they perform poorly. The study further stressed that poor performance is not only frustrating to the students and parents, but also affects the society in terms of quality manpower in all spheres of the economy and politics.

Despite all these arrays of benefits as supported by most empirical studies indicating that computer graphics improves memory for the illustrated information and comprehension of the situation described in the text (Geer, 2012) teachers are yet to fully adopt its use. According to Brendon (2018), while teachers are expected to integrate technology into the classroom, the reality can be very different. Furthermore, studies as shown in literature indicate that prevailing teaching strategies predominantly employed by most teachers of woodworking technology in Nigeria are largely teacher-centered, involving mostly description of abstract phenomenon. This is perceived to be narrow in orientation, teacher dominated, archaic and does not encourage students to be creative since context-based learning through practical problem-solving approaches hardly occurs; in addition to this development is that the Colleges of Education in Nigeria produce very weak teachers (Ada, 2012).

The Philosophy and objectives of the Nigeria Certificate in Education (Technical) programme as captured in the NCE minimum standards for Vocational and Technical Education essentially seeks to provide technical teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for teaching technical subjects and to make them adoptable to any changing situation in technological development not only in the country but also in the world at large (NCCE minimum standard, 2020 Edition). Similarly, Machine woodworking with the code TED 212; it is a two (2) credit course offered by all 200 level NCE (Technical Education) students. The specific objectives of the course as stipulated in the NCCE minimum standard is basically to introduce students to various types of Woodworking Machines as well as equip them with both their sequence of operations and their principles of operation. It is against these backdrops that the study seeks to determine the cognitive achievements of students after being taught with the developed computer graphic animation courseware developed to enhance the teaching and conceptual understanding of Machine woodworking at the (NCE) level in North West Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The inability to fully achieve the noble national objectives of Technical and Vocational Education can be attributed to the general prevailing teaching strategies predominantly employed by teachers in the Colleges; the teaching strategies used in technical education courses are mostly traditional teaching methods which in the views of Igor (2020) are focused on the teacher as the only sources of information. Consequently, Abid, Javard, Mohd, & Rajiv (2022), opined that traditional classroom instruction falls short of providing an immediate learning environment, faster evaluation and more engagement.

Equally, Yerima & Mshelia, (2023), corroborated these views in a study and posited that such teaching strategies are largely devoid of the use of technological applications which has been proven to have the capacity to create high quality learning environment and yields better results. Additionally, the study submitted that the prevailing teaching strategies used by Machine woodworking teachers are largely teacher centered involving mostly description of abstract phenomena; they are narrow in orientation, uninspiring, un-engaging, un-instructive and archaic thereby resulting in the abysmally poor conceptual understanding of the basic working principles of woodworking Machine by NCE (Technical) students. There is no doubt that this trend has the capacity to hinder the achievement of the overall goals of Technical and Vocational Education. Furthermore, Abid et al. (2022) opined that digital learning tools and technologies have the capacity to fill this void as some of the efficiencies such technologies provide are simply unrivalled by traditional learning methodologies. It is therefore imperative that schools, educational institutions and technical teachers in particular adopts and make efficient use of different electronic technology applications in the classroom to ensure better learning environment and better learning outcomes.

Purpose of the Study

The primary purpose of the study was to determine the effect of a computer graphic animation courseware used in the teaching of Machine woodworking in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the effect of a computer graphic animation on students' cognitive achievement of students in the Experimental group after undergoing treatment.

Research Question

1. What are the Mean cognitive achievement scores of students taught Machine woodworking in the Experimental and Control groups in North West Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H0₁: There is no significant difference between the Mean cognitive achievement scores of NCE students taught Machine woodworking in the Experimental group in pretest and post test.

H0₂: There is no significant difference between the mean cognitive achievement scores of NCE students taught Machine woodworking in the Experimental and Control groups in post test.

Literature Review

The theoretical framework on which this study was hinged is the cognitive theory of multimedia learning which was propounded by Mayer & Moreno in 1999. The cognitive theory of multimedia learning states that deeper learning can occur when information is presented in both text and graphics than by text alone. Additionally, Mayer's study (as cited by Wiley 2016) dictates that "humans possess separate channels for processing visual and auditory information". The first is the visual – pictorial channel, which processes images seen through the eye (including words displayed on screen). The other channel is the auditory – verbal channel, which processes spoken words.

The conceptual framework was structured to basically establish the causal relationship between a Computer Graphic Animation Courseware (CGAC) and the cognitive Achievement of NCE (Technical) students in Machine woodworking. The CGAC instrument was developed to facilitate the teaching and learning as well as the conceptual understanding of the basic

principles of operation of various woodworking machines at the NCE level in line with the Cognitive theory of Multimedia learning which submits that people learn more deeply from words and pictures than from words alone.

The review of empirical studies brought to the fore the fact that most of the researches focused on the application of graphic animations to facilitate learning processes at either the Primary or Secondary school levels with a very few targeted at Tertiary institutions. Similarly, the locations of the researches were mostly in Asia, Europe, America and some African countries with non-targeting a Nigerian population. In addition, the studies reviewed focused mostly in Mathematics, Science and Engineering with non-focusing generally on Technology related fields and Machine woodworking in particular. This was the identified gap this study offers to fill by the deliberate attempt to determine the effect of the developed CGAC instrument on the Cognitive Achievement of NCE students in Machine Woodworking.

Methodology

A research design according Shana (2022) is a strategy for answering your research questions using empirical data and also allows the researcher to test cause and effect relationships. The study deployed the quasi- experimental research design which essentially involves the pretest and post -test non-equivalent control group, and quasi experimental study. The main reason for adopting the non-equivalent control group, quasi experimental design is simply because of the use of existing classrooms in a school for a study without creating classroom groups through random selection and random assignment. According to Borg and Gall (2014), quasi –experimental design can be used when it is not possible for the researcher to randomly sample the subjects and assign them to treatment groups without disrupting the academic program of the school involved in the study.

The actual study was conducted in North West Nigeria covering all the public Colleges of Education in the zone. The North West geopolitical zone consists of seven (7) states namely: Kaduna, Kano, Jigawa, Katsina, Zamfara, Sokoto and Kebbi states. The study was limited to the North West Geo-Political Zone of Nigeria. The population for the stud consisted of the entire 137 200 level NCE students offering Woodwork Technology in all the 12 public Colleges of Education in North Western Nigeria. Four (4) Machine Woodwork course lecturers were involved as the resource persons for both the control and experimental groups. The researcher used the random sampling procedure in selecting four (4) out of 12 Colleges of Education that will be involved in the study. Two Colleges were used as the experimental group while the other two will be used as the control group. In all, 137 students participated in the study and a total of 4 woodwork teachers who are assigned to teach Machine woodworking (TED 212) participated in the study as research assistant involved in the treatment and actual teaching of the course. The pretest item was used to ascertain the entry behaviour of all the students in both the experimental and control groups. The same procedure was used for the post-test, although the questions were rearranged. The post-test was used to determine the effect of the Computer Graphic Animation Courseware (CGAC) on students' Cognitive achievement after the treatment. The study adopted the CGAC developed by Yerima & Mshelia, (2023).

Data for the study was collected through the pretest items which were administered to students before the treatment to measure the group equivalence and that provided the researcher with the baseline data about the subject while post-test was administered on students one week after treatment. All the instruments were administered through the respective course lecturers that served as research assistance after undergoing adequate training. Furthermore, the method of data collection adopted ensured a 100% return rate achievement. The treatment lasted for four weeks and the post –test items was administered one week after. The items were the same with the pretest items except for that the 20 items were re –arranged to give an outlook of newness. Both the experimental and control groups participated in the post-test and the results obtained

were analyzed for the purpose of determining the effect of the developed computer animation courseware on students cognitive achievement.

The Machine woodworking Achievement Test items (MWWAT) and the Computer Graphic Animation Suitability Questionnaire (CGASQ) were validated by four (4) experts who were requested to check the appropriateness of the all the test items to ensure that the items are not ambiguous. The experts were from Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, University of Lagos, Kaduna Polytechnic, Kaduna and the Kaduna State College of Education, Gidanwaya. All their observations and corrections were incorporated in the final draft of the test items. The lesson plan was also validated by experts and their comments and suggestions were also incorporated in the final draft of the lesson plan.

The instruments for data collection were used during the pilot study in Colleges of Education from other zones that will not be involved in the actual study. According to Amos (2016), reliability is the degree of consistency with which an instrument measures whatever it measures; hence, the pilot study was conducted and the data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha coefficient with the SPSS version 25. The computed values for the items both the MWWAT and CGASQ were .983 and .993. The high values obtained indicated that all the five instruments were reliable as opined by Cohen as cited in Daud (2018) that reliability coefficient value of 0.70 to 0.99 is sufficiently enough for taking decisions on the internal consistency of items in an instrument.

Data collected from the test items were analyzed using Mean (M), Standard Deviation (SD) and the independent sample t- test statistics. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using the independent sample t-test to compare the means of the groups and for hypothesis testing. According to the Kent State University SPSS tutorials, the independent sample t-test compares the means of two independent groups in order to determine whether there is statistical evidence that associated population means are significantly different. The independent sample t-test is a parametric test. The p-value Hypothesis testing provides that if the p- value for the calculated sample value of the test statistics is less than the chosen significance level α , reject the null hypothesis at significance level α $p\text{-value} < \alpha \Rightarrow \text{reject } H_0$ at significance level α . This therefore implies that the Means of the two groups are different.

Results

The results of the data analyzed were presented, interpreted and discussed. The presentation follows the order of the research questions.

Research Question 1

What are the Mean cognitive achievement scores of students taught Machine woodworking in the Experimental and Control groups in North West Nigeria?

Answer to the above research question is provided in Tables 1

Table 1: Mean and standard Deviation in of paired statistical analysis of the effect of computer graphic animation on students’ cognitive achievements.

Group	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Control Group	21.20	6.846	52.57	5.419
Experimental Group	29.56	11.196	66.04	6.259

KEY: M = Mean, SD = Standard deviation

Fig 1: Data in table 1 present in Bar chart

Data in table 1 and fig 1 shows the Mean and Standard deviation values of student’s cognitive achievements in both the experimental and the control groups. The data also presents the group statistic that shows the effects of the computer graphic animation courseware on students’ cognitive achievements in pretest and post -test for both experimental and control groups. The table showed pretest Mean for experimental group at 29.56 and a standard deviation value of 11.20 while the Mean value of the control group stands at 21.20 and a standard deviation of 6.84. The difference was 13.48. On the other hand, the table showed a post- test Mean for experimental group at 66.04 and a standard deviation of 6.289 while the Mean value for the control group stands at 52.57 with standard deviation at 5.419 indicating that the computer graphic animation courseware developed for teaching Machines Woodworking in Colleges of Education had a positive effect on student’s cognitive achievements.

Test of Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the Mean cognitive achievement scores of NCE students taught Machine woodworking in the Experimental group in pretest and post test.

Table 2: Independent t –test analysis

Group	Pre-test		Post-test		T	d.f	p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Experimental Group	29.56	11.196	66.04	6.259	-27.117	90	.0001*

KEY: M = Mean, SD = Standard deviation, t = calculated t- value, df = Degree of freedom, p – value = probability value

Data presented in Table 2 shows the paired sample statistics of both pretest and post test results in the experimental group. The pretest mean scores obtained stands at 29.560 and the post test stands at 66.044 indicating a mean gain of 36.484. Indicating that the students’ scores for pretest and post-test are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). This implies that the p-value of 0.001 which is less than the 0.005 level of significance shows that a significant difference exists in favour of the Post test. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

H0₂ There is no significant difference between the mean cognitive achievement scores of NCE students taught Machine woodworking in Experimental and Control groups in post test.

Table 3: Independent sample t-test (control and experimental group)

Group	Mean	SD	Difference	t	d.f	p-value
Control Group	52.57	5.42	13.48	-12.43	135	.0001*
Experimental Group	66.04	6.26				

KEY: M = Mean, SD = Standard deviation, t = calculated t- value, df = Degree of freedom, p – value = probability value

Data in Table 3 shows the Independent paired Sample t- test of post test for both experimental and control groups. The post-test Mean scores of the two groups were compared using the independent paired sample t-test. The results shows that control group sample ($M = 52.5652$, $SD = 5.41870$) reported lower achievement ($t = -13.038$, $p = .0001$, $d = 13.47874$) than the experimental group sample ($M = 66.0440$, $SD = 6.25906$) indicating that the students’ Mean scores for post-test are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). In other words, the result revealed that for the experimental group sample $t = -13.038$, $P = .0001$, $\alpha = 0.05$ is indicating that the students’ Mean scores for post-test are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). This difference can be observed further from the Mean and Standard Deviation of the total scores obtained in post-tests and the significance (P-value) obtained. It is concluded that since the p- value .0001 is less than 0.05; then therefore, there exists a significance differences, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Findings of the Study

The following findings came out based on the results of the analysis of the study:

1. The evaluation process was successfully implemented before and after the treatment and the experimental group performed better. The empirical evidence provided the bases for inference to be made to the effect that the use of the CGAC instrument was responsible for the improved performance of the experimental group over the control group.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study it was concluded that the Computer Graphic Animation Courseware (CGAC) was effective and can be widely applied in the teaching and learning of Machine Woodworking in Colleges of Education in Nigeria since there is verifiable empirical evidence. Furthermore, the application and use of the developed CGAC instrument should be extended to the Technical Colleges and the University system.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The methods and strategies used in the learning process of Machine Woodworking should be enhanced through the use of electronic learning instruments by adopting and deploying the developed Computer Graphic Animation Courseware (CGAC) instrument. Findings from this study has provided empirical evidence to the effective of the instrument; consequently. The National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), Woodworking teachers and lecturers teaching should embrace its use to ensure better teaching and learning environment, better conceptual understanding of the basic principles of operations of Woodworking machines and greater students cognitive achievements.

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